

1 SCENARIO APPLYING SPI-MEF

1.1 Background

One Solution is a software company specialized in banking and financial solution software. The company has expertise in producing software for banks, insurances, mortgage and financial applications with clients dispersed all across Scandinavian countries. Software produced by One Solution includes Internet Banking System, Loan System, Deposit System, Mobile Banking System and front-end office for banking and also systems for a central mainframe platform.

One Solution has approximately 900 employees dispersed geographically in Sweden, Denmark, Norway and Finland. Product development at One Solution is divided into varied sizes of projects. A typical product consists of 1-3 projects with approximately 5-10 full-time staff working in one project a time. All projects follow the Waterfall model as software development life-cycle.

One Solution's organizational structure consists of three layers. The top layer consists of corporate shareholders and top level managers (President, Vice President, etc.). Top level managers coordinate the middle organization layer which consists of head of departments. Departments within One Solution are divided into two functional units, the Research & Development (R&D) and the Support.

R&D is responsible for the development of One Solution products, whereas Support is not directly related with One Solution's core business but supports and implements operational activities (e.g. Marketing Department, Human Resource Department, Finance Department, etc). R&D is led by one head of department which coordinates departments that are responsible for One Solution products (e.g. Department of Internet Banking, Department of Loan System, Department of Deposit System, etc.). R&D includes also a process group that is responsible for the implementation of software process improvements in product development.

Each of the development departments under R&D and the process group has low-level managers, which occupy the roles of project managers and product managers. These managers are responsible for the operation of project and product development. Within the process group are SPI coordinators who are responsible for the assimilation and adoption of new processes or technologies in all developments within the R&D departments.

One Solution's highest priority is customer satisfaction. Their customers demand high quality software and fast delivery time to achieve their goals as the domain is quite competitive. In order to fulfill their customers' needs, One Solution aims to increase the maturity of their processes by following the CMMI standard. Recently, One Solution has been assessed at CMMI Maturity Level 2 according to CMMI scale, and their goal is to increase their CMMI maturity level to Level 3 with the objective to deliver better products to their customers and increase their satisfaction.

A preliminary assessment for CMMI Level 3 showed that One Solution was still lacking in three key process areas (KPA). Those KPAs are listed below:

- *Product Integration (PI)*
The purpose of Product Integration (PI) is to assemble the product from the product components, ensure that the product, as integrated, functions properly, and deliver the product.
- *Verification (VER)*
The purpose of Verification (VER) is to ensure that selected work products meet their specified requirements.
- *Validation (VAL)*
The purpose of Validation (VAL) is to demonstrate that a product or product component fulfills its intended use when placed in its intended environment.

To address these KPAs, One Solution has decided to adopt several improvement actions. Those actions are listed below:

i. Peer Review Process

Peer review is an important activity in verification for effective defect detection. The type of peer review taken in this improvement is inspection. Inspection is a review of work products by trained individuals who want to find defects using a well-defined process. The inspection process requires training on the process change, methodologies and tools.

ii. Unit Test Planning

Unit testing is found not to be properly conducted and thus many critical defects that should have been detected and resolved in the implementation phase escaped to later phases or were even shipped to the customer. Therefore, the process is expanded to include unit test plans so that the task can be performed more effectively. The unit test plan will contain a systematic approach on the creation of unit test cases during the design and coding phases and a specified test coverage goal must be achieved before going to the next development phase. Unit test planning also requires training on the process change, methodologies and tools.

iii. Developmental Integration Testing (DIT)

The components of the various software products are developed by different development teams in different projects. An integration of these components requires developmental integration testing (DIT). DIT is intended to expose defects in the interfaces and the interaction among integrated components. DIT includes the planning and execution of tests in an environment when the various components are integrated. The developmental integration testing also requires training on the process change, methodologies and tools.

iv. Support Tool for Software Development

The current bug tracking was done manually, which led to chaotic bug documentation. In order to solve this problem, a support tool for bug tracking needs to be implemented. The support tool will provide a systematic way of bug tracking and thus improve the software development process.

The initiatives will be rolled out in three phases according to the target entities where the actions are implemented (Figure 1). Later phases have broader scope, i.e. they address a

higher number of target entities. The reason for choosing this strategy is to gain better control on the improvement process. Starting with a smaller scope and then expand the initiatives to more target entities will help to manage the risk of failing initiatives or changes that do not perform as well as expected. Implementing the initiatives in three phases also allows applying refinements from one phase to another such that successive implementations succeed with a higher probability.

Figure 1: SPI-MEF stages applied in scenario phases

1.1.1 Initialization – Gather SPI initiative information

In the initialization stage, the information about the SPI initiative in One Solution is gathered and the *SPI Initiative Form* is filled in:

Table 1: *SPI Initiative Form* for One Solution

SPI Initiative Form	
Type of SPI Initiative	: SPI Frameworks
Name	: Capability Maturity Model Integrated (CMMI)
Current Maturity Level	: Level 2
Description	: Improvement Practices (see Section 1.1): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Peer Review Process 2. Unit Test Planning 3. Development Integration Testing 4. Support Tool for Software Development
Improvement Goals	: The improvement goal is aimed to meet customer satisfaction in two aspects: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve product quality 2. Decrease time-to-delivery
Key Process Area (KPA)	: The following KPAs are being addressed with the improvement practices (see Section 1.1): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Product Integration 2. Verification 3. Validation
Target Entities for Implementation	: The implementation of the process change will be carried out in three phases. Each phases are distinguished as follows: Phase 1: Pilot projects in Internet Banking System development

	<p>Phase 2: Expand to all projects in Internet Banking System development</p> <p>Phase 3: Further expand to all projects in the following development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Loan System ✓ Deposit System
Implementation Schedule	<p>Phase 1: Starting from June 2006 until December 2006 (6 months)</p> <p>Phase 2: Starting from January 2007 onwards</p> <p>Phase 3: Starting from January 2008 onwards</p>

1.1.2 Initialization – Gap analysis of evaluation quality

In this step, the historical data gained in previous evaluations conducted by One Solution is analyzed. The assessment was conducted when the company decided to acquire the CMMI Level 2 certification. From the available historical data it is evident that One Solution only evaluated the performance of their processes at the Process and Project levels. Meetings with the employees in charge of the current measurement program within the SPI process group revealed that the collected measurements were defined ad-hoc, following best practices established in industry. In particular, following the definition of SPI-MEF, they only considered primary measurements, without considering complementary measurements and confounding factors. Knowing this fact, the current position of One Solution in the evaluation opportunity matrix is located in the area where accuracy is low and coverage is at an average level.

One Solution decides to achieve a holistic evaluation with high accuracy and wide coverage in order to benefit in the long-term from the improved evaluation process, which is, achieving confidence that the improvement initiatives provide the expected outcome and provide indeed value to their customers. A meeting with representatives of the stakeholders of the SPI initiatives, the SPI process group and the measurement team resulted in the definition of the path that One Solution is going to follow to evaluate the forthcoming SPI initiatives. The decision is based on the company's setting (primarily cost, time and available resources) and is also constrained by the phases that One Solution has already defined to roll-out the initiatives. Based on this information, the path that One Solution takes for evaluating the improvement is starting from achieving accuracy first and then addressing coverage. The path that One Solution is going to take towards the holistic view is shown in the Figure 2.

The evaluation of the first and second phases in the initiatives implementation is aimed to achieve high accuracy. Coverage is not aimed at this point since in the scope of those phases in terms of target entities is limited and it is assumed that the effect of the improvement will not yet be visible at the Product or Organizational Level. Besides, cost is also considered for this decision since the top-level management of One Solution is still reluctant to approve the resources for a broader evaluation before the accuracy of evaluations is improved. Therefore, starting with the evaluation in two measurement levels, Process and Project, in an accurate way is deemed as more reasonable than choosing to evaluate all measurement levels.

Evaluation Opportunity Matrix for One Solution

Figure 2: *Evaluation Opportunity Matrix* for One Solution

The evaluation of the third phase is anticipated to have a wider coverage as compared to the previous ones. The considered measurement levels include all measurement levels defined by SPI-MEF. The reason for having a wider coverage is that the effects of the improvement have propagated to the Product and Organizational level. Furthermore, the evaluation team assumes at that moment, that the top-level management is willing to provide more resources for the evaluation after seeing the results of the previous two evaluations.

1.2 Phase I

In this phase the initiatives are implemented in pilot projects. The objective of having one phase for piloting the initiatives in projects is to see whether the changed processes are applicable to the typical projects in One Solution and to discover any adaptability issues which can then be addressed in the following phases. Four pilot projects within Internet Banking Department are selected for this phase's implementation.

1.2.1 Design – Evaluation scoping

In this step, the scoping is done by considering two measurement levels, Project and Process, and all stakeholders that are interested to see the evaluation result of those two levels. There are four stakeholders interested in this evaluation: SPI Coordinator, Head of Internet Banking Department, Development Teams and the Project Managers of the pilot projects.

In the Process level, the SPI Coordinator needs to know the compliance and adaptability of the process to define what refinements need to be implemented in order to allow a smooth introduction of the changes in the following phases. The SPI Coordinator needs to report to the Head of Internet Banking Department. The Head of Internet Banking Department needs to see the result of evaluation as he is the one who takes decisions for the next implementation phase in his department. The Development Teams who are implementing the

initiatives see the evaluation results as it motivates to adapt the changes and increases their commitment.

In the Project level, the Project Managers, as the ones who coordinate the entire processes within the pilot projects, need to see the evaluation results because they need to judge and gauge the change from the introduced processes as how they impact the projects in general. The Head of Department, as the superior of the Project Managers, is interested to see the result in this level because he decides which of the initiatives will be implemented in the following phase. The Development Teams of the pilot projects who are coordinated by the Project Managers need to know evaluation results to know the effect of the initiatives at the project scope so that they can be motivated for these improvement initiatives.

Table 2: Phase I: *Evaluation Area Table*

Measurement Levels	Viewpoints		
	<i>Implementer</i>	<i>Coordinator</i>	<i>Sponsor</i>
Process	Development Team (Architect, Analyst, Programmer, Tester)	SPI Coordinator	Head of Department (Internet Banking System)
Project	Development Team (Architect, Analyst, Programmer, Tester)	Project Managers (Internet Banking System)	Head of Department (Internet Banking System)

1.2.2 Design – Determination of measures

From the *SPI Initiative Form*, it is known that there are two improvement goals for the introduced SPI initiatives. Since there are two separate improvement goals, the determination of measures will be performed separately for each improvement goal. For BG1: Improve product quality the GQM Construction Table (Table 3) is populated first and then the GQM approach is applied as shown in Table 4. The same approach is followed for BG2: Decrease time-to-deliver as shown in Table 5 and Table 6 respectively.

Table 3: Phase I: *GQM Construction Table* for BG1

Purpose:	Evaluate			
Business Goal (Improvement Goal):	BG1: Improve product quality			
Object of Study:	CMMI: 1. Peer Review Process 2. Unit Test Planning 3. Development Integration Testing 4. Support Tool for Software Development			
Context:	Pilot projects in Internet Banking System			
Measurement Level	Point of View (Viewpoint)	Category	Focus (Success Indicator)	Measurement Goal
Process	SPI Coordinator	Primary	Effectiveness	MG01_PRC

		Complementary	Efficiency	MG02_PRC
			Process Conformance*	MG03_PRC
	Development Team	Primary	Effectiveness	MG04_PRC
	Head of Department	Primary	Effectiveness	MG05_PRC
Project	Project Manager	Primary	Defects	MG01_PRJ
		Complementary	Cost/Effort	MG02_PRJ
	Development Team	Primary	Defects	MG03_PRJ
	Head of Department	Primary	Defects	MG04_PRJ

(*) *Process conformance is not a success indicator for the evaluation but in this phase where the SPI initiatives are piloted, it is an important Focus to assist the evaluation. This is done by looking at the degree of the process conformance and it gives the confidence on how much the impact can be attributed to the SPI initiatives.*

Table 4: Phase I: *Measurement Goal, Question(s) and Metrics* for BG1

MG01_PRC: Effectiveness

Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their effectiveness in defect detection on pilot projects from the SPI Coordinator point of view.

Question 1: What is the number of defects found by the peer review process in terms of its effectiveness?

Metrics:

M01_PRC:

Phase Containment Effectiveness for Phase i (PCE i)

$$PCE\ i = F / (F + E)$$

F = Number of defects found in phase i

E = Number of defects escaped from phase i

i = Requirement, Design, Coding, Unit Test

This metric shows the phase containment effectiveness for a certain phase during the development. Conducting peer reviews is expected to retain more defects from escaping to the next development phases.

Question 2: What is, in overall, the number of defects found by the introduced SPI initiatives (peer review process, unit test planning and development integration testing) in terms of their effectiveness?

Metrics:

M02_PRC:

Defect detection effectiveness before system test

Defect detection effectiveness before system test = A / B

A = Total number of actual high severity defects found before system test

B = Total number of actual high severity defects found before delivery to customer

High severity defect = Defect that causes crash or misbehaviour of the intended function.

This metric shows the effectiveness of the defect detection processes (peer review process, unit test planning and development integration testing) during the development before

entering the system test phase.

Notes: Since the initiatives are introduced simultaneously it is impossible to reliably assess the effect of a single initiative. Therefore, in Question 2, the initiatives are addressed as a whole. The development life-cycle of One Solution allows an exception: since the Waterfall model is applied, the development phases are conducted in sequence; therefore it is assumed to be possible to assess the effectiveness of the peer reviews (Question 1) since no other initiative will interfere with it and influence the outcome. The same principle applies to the next measurement goal, process efficiency.

MG02_PRC: Efficiency

Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of its efficiency in defect detection on pilot projects from the SPI Coordinator point of view.

Question 1: What is the number of defects found by the peer review process in terms of its efficiency?

Metrics:

M03_PRC:

Defect removal efficiency, DRE before Unit Test

$$\text{DRE before Unit Test} = E / (E+D)$$

E = Total number of defects found before Unit Test

D = Total number of defects found after Unit Test

This metric shows the defect removal efficiency with the help of the peer review process before entering the unit test phase.

Question 2: What is the number of defects found by the introduced SPI initiatives (peer review process, unit test planning and development integration testing) in terms of their efficiency?

Metrics:

M04_PRC:

Defect removal efficiency, DRE

$$\text{DRE} = E / (E+D)$$

E = Total number of defects found before delivery to customer

D = Total number of defects found after delivery to customer

This metric shows the defect removal efficiency of the SPI initiatives (peer review process, unit test planning and development integration testing) cumulatively. The initiatives are expected to increase the number of defects found before delivering the product to customers.

MG03_PRC: Process Conformance

Evaluate the SPI initiatives with respect to its conformance to the specified standard process in the pilot projects from the SPI Coordinator point of view.

Question 1: What is the degree of process compliance of the SPI initiatives when they are implemented?

Metrics:

M05_PRC:

Checklist-based rating for each process

Each SPI initiative will have a pre-defined checklist containing a list of standards or requirements that need to be followed. The rating will **not be used for evaluating** the success of the SPI implementation but it is intended to be used along-side with the evaluation results to judge how much the improvement can be attributed to the implemented process change.

MG04_PRC: Effectiveness

Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG01_PRC, point of view is the Development Team.

MG05_PRC: Effectiveness

Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG01_PRC, point of view is the Head of Department.

MG01_PRJ: Defects

Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their impact on the number of encountered defects in the pilot projects from the Project Manager point of view.

Question 1: What is the number of defects in the work products in the pilot projects?

Metrics:

M01_PRJ:

Defect density, DD for Phase *i*

$DD \text{ for Phase } i = N / S$

N = Number of defects in the work products of the respective development phases

S = Project size calculated in lines-of-codes (LOC)

i = Requirement, Design, Coding, Unit Test, Integration

This metric shows the number of defects in each phase normalized by the project size. With the introduction of the new SPI initiatives, the defect density of later development phases (e.g. Coding and Unit Test) is expected to be lowered as compared to previous projects because the peer review activities are expected to prevent defects from escaping to the next phases.

MG02_PRJ: Cost/Effort

Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their impact on the resources needed in the pilot projects from the Project Manager point of view.

Question 1: What is the actual effort that is required to develop the pilot projects?

Metrics:

M02_PRJ:

Total project effort normalized by project size

Total project effort normalized by project size = $\frac{\text{Actual project effort}}{\text{Actual project size}}$

This metric shows the total effort in the development of the pilot projects. This metric will indicate if there is any significant effort that is required to incorporate the introduction of the new SPI initiatives.

MG03_PRJ: Defects

Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG01_PRJ, point of view is the Development Team.

MG04_PRJ: Defects

Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG01_PRJ, point of view is the Head of Department.

Table 5: Phase I: *GQM Construction Table* for BG2

Purpose:	Evaluate			
Business Goal (Improvement Goal):	BG2: Decrease time-to-deliver			
Object of Study:	CMMI: 1. Peer Review Process 2. Unit Test Planning 3. Development Integration Testing 4. Support Tool for Software Development			
Context:	Pilot projects in Internet Banking System			
Measurement Level	Point of View (Viewpoint)	Category	Focus (Success Indicator)	Measurement Goal
Process	SPI Coordinator	Primary	Efficiency	MG06_PRC
		Complementary	Effectiveness	MG07_PRC
			Process Conformance*	MG08_PRC
	Development Team	Primary	Efficiency	MG09_PRC
	Head of Department	Primary	Efficiency	MG10_PRC
Project	Project Manager	Primary	Schedule	MG05_PRJ
		Complementary	Defects	MG06_PRJ
	Development Team	Primary	Schedule	MG07_PRJ
	Head of Department	Primary	Schedule	MG08_PRJ

(*) *Process conformance is not a success indicator for the evaluation but in this phase where the SPI initiatives are piloted, it is an important Focus to assist the evaluation. This is done by looking at the degree of the process conformance and it gives the confidence on how much the impact can be attributed to the SPI initiatives.*

Table 6: Phase I: *Measurement Goal, Question(s) and Metrics* for BG2

<p>MG06_PRC: Efficiency Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG02_PRC, point of view is the SPI Coordinator.</p>
<p>MG07_PRC: Effectiveness Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG01_PRC, point of view is the SPI Coordinator.</p>
<p>MG08_PRC: Process Conformance Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG03_PRC, point of view is the SPI Coordinator.</p>
<p>MG09_PRC: Efficiency Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG02_PRC, point of view is the Development Team.</p>

<p>MG10_PRC: Efficiency Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG02_PRC, point of view is the Head of Department.</p>
<p>MG05_PRJ: Schedule Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their impact on project schedule of the pilot projects from the Project Manager point of view.</p> <p>Question 1: What is the actual project schedule for the pilot projects?</p> <p>Metrics:</p> <p>M03_PRJ: Project cycle-time normalized by project size Project cycle-time normalized by project size = $\frac{\text{Actual project cycle-time}}{\text{Actual project size}}$</p> <p>This metric gives the total project cycle-time in the development of the pilot projects, normalized by the project size. This metric will indicate if there is any significant delay in the usual project cycle-time after incorporating the new SPI initiatives.</p>
<p>MG06_PRJ: Defects Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG01_PRJ, point of view is the Project Manager.</p>
<p>MG07_PRJ: Schedule Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG05_PRJ, point of view is the Development Team.</p>
<p>MG08_PRJ: Schedule Reuse of the same Questions and Metrics from MG05_PRJ, point of view is the Head of Department.</p>

Figure 3 illustrates the GQM Tree for Phase I which enhances the traceability of the elicited metrics to the respective measurement and business goal.

Figure 3: GQM tree for Phase I

1.2.3 Design – Selection of evaluation methods

In this step, the evaluation methods for each metric are defined. The metrics alongside with their properties and applied evaluation methods is documented in the *Metric Form*. Table 7, Table 8 and Table 9 below show examples of the *Metric Form* for metrics M01_PRC, M04_PRC and M03_PRJ defined in the previous step.

Table 7: Phase I: *Metric Form* for M01_PRC

Metric Form	
Metric ID	: M01_PRC
Metric Name	: Phase Containment Effectiveness for Phase <i>i</i> (PCE <i>i</i>)
Success Indicator	: Effectiveness
Measurement Goal (Viewpoint)	: i. MG01_PRC (SPI Coordinator) ii. MG04_PRC (Development Team) iii. MG05_PRC (Head of Department) iv. MG07_PRC (SPI Coordinator)
Measurement Level	: Process
Algorithm / Description	: $PCE\ i = F / (F + E)$ F = Number of defects found in phase <i>i</i> E = Number of defects escaped from phase <i>i</i> <i>i</i> = Requirement, Design, Coding, Unit Test This metric shows the phase containment effectiveness for certain phase during the development. Conducting peer reviews is expected to retain more defects from escaping to the next development phases. Example: The number of defects found in Coding phase is 30 defects and the number of defects that managed to escape from Coding phase is 15. Therefore, the PCE Coding = $30 / (30 + 15) = 66\%$
Baseline Value	: The baselines for this metric can be computed based on the data collected from previous projects or calculated from current projects (without the SPI initiative implemented) that are running. Based on the historical data in the organization, the baseline values for PCE are: PCE Requirement = 60% PCE Design = 50% PCE Coding = 55% PCE Unit Test = 40%
Deviation Range	: The deviation range for the respective phases is $\pm 10\%$.
Evaluation Method	: Pre-post comparison Objective: The evaluation is aimed to find out if the SPI initiatives are able to increase the value of PCE in the development phases of the pilot projects.
Confounding Factor(s)	: During pre-post comparison, the following factors should be taken into consideration in the evaluation: 1. Project size and complexity (LOC, No. of features)

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Technology factors (Language, tool, environment, platform) 3. Employee factors (Level of experience, turnover) 4. Process Compliance (Degree of process conformance implemented and followed)
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Table 8: Phase I: *Metric Form* for M04_PRC

Metric Form	
Metric ID	: M04_PRC
Metric Name	: Defect removal efficiency, DRE
Success Indicator	: Efficiency
Measurement Goal (Viewpoint)	: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. MG02_PRC (SPI Coordinator) ii. MG06_PRC (SPI Coordinator) iii. MG09_PRC (Development Team) iv. MG10_PRC (Head of Department)
Measurement Level	: Process
Algorithm / Description	: <p>$DRE = E / (E+D)$</p> <p>E = Total number of defects found before delivery to customer D = Total number of defects found after delivery to customer</p> <p>This metric shows the defect removal efficiency of the SPI initiatives (peer review process, unit test planning and development integration testing) cumulatively. The initiatives are expected to increase the number of defects found before delivering the product to customers.</p> <p>Example: The number of defects found before delivery is 120 defects and the number of defects that are reported by the customer is 45. Therefore, the $DRE = 120 / (120 + 45) = 73\%$</p>
Baseline Value	: The baselines for this metric can be computed based on the data collected from previous projects or calculated from current projects (without the SPI initiative implemented) that are running. Based on the historical data in the organization, the baseline value for DRE is 75%.
Deviation Range	: The deviation range is set to $\pm 10\%$.
Evaluation Method	: <p>Pre-post comparison</p> <p>Objective: The evaluation is aimed to find out if the SPI initiatives are able to increase the value of DRE in the pilot projects.</p>
Confounding Factor(s)	: <p>During pre-post comparison, the following factors should be taken into consideration in the evaluation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project size and complexity (LOC, No. of features) 2. Technology factors (Language, tool, environment, platform) 3. Employee factors (Level of experience, turnover) 4. Process Compliance (Degree of process conformance implemented and followed)

Table 9: Phase I: *Metric Form* for M03_PRJ

Metric Form	
Metric ID	: M03_PRJ
Metric Name	: Project cycle-time normalized by project size
Success Indicator	: Schedule
Measurement Goal (Viewpoint)	: i. MG05_PRC (Project Manager) ii. MG07_PRC (Development Team) iii. MG08_PRC (Head of Department)
Measurement Level	: Project
Algorithm / Description	: Project cycle-time normalized by project size = Actual project cycle-time / Actual project size This metric gives the total project cycle-time in the development of the pilot projects, normalized by the project size. This metric will indicate if there is any significant delay in the usual project cycle-time after incorporating the new SPI initiatives. Example: The project size is 10 KLOC and the actual project cycle-time is 3.5 months. Therefore, the project cycle-time normalized by project size = $3.5 / 10 = 0.35$ months per KLOC.
Baseline Value	: The baselines for this metric can be computed based on the data collected from previous projects or calculated from current projects (without the SPI initiative implemented) that are running. Based on the historical data in the organization, the baseline value for project cycle-time normalized by project size is 0.20 months per KLOC.
Deviation Range	: The deviation range is set to $\pm 20\%$.
Evaluation Method	: Pre-post comparison Objective: The evaluation is aimed to find out if the SPI initiatives affects the project cycle-time in the pilot projects.
Confounding Factor(s)	: During pre-post comparison, the following factors should be taken into consideration in the evaluation: 1. Project size and complexity (LOC, No. of features) 2. Technology factors (Language, tool, environment, platform) 3. Employee factors (Level of experience, turnover) 4. Process Compliance (Degree of process conformance implemented and followed)

1.2.4 Design – Evaluation scheduling

After the required metrics have been defined, the evaluation on the pilot projects can now be scheduled as shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Phase I: *Evaluation Scheduling Form*

Duration:	Starting from June 2006 until December 2006 (6 months)			
Context:	<p>There are 4 pilot projects in the Internet Banking System Department that have been selected for the evaluation. The 4 projects have the following schedule:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) Project I: 30th June 2006 – 25th August 2006 ii) Project II: 13th July 2006 – 30th August 2006 iii) Project III: 5th September 2006 – 5th November 2006 iv) Project IV: 9th November 2006 – 28th December 2006 <p>Note: In order to effectively pilot out the SPI initiatives in the projects within the Internet Banking System Department, the above projects are selected based on the same staffs who are working on these projects, i.e. staffs working in Project I and III, and II and IV are the same. Proper rolling out of the SPI initiatives is performed that includes training sessions and written guidelines for staffs who are working on these projects.</p>			
Time to evaluate / Periodic evaluation	Measurement Levels	Lag Factor (LF)	Degradation Factor (DF)	Time to Evaluate
	Project	<p>4 months</p> <p>The usual project cycle-time for Internet Banking development is around three months and one month in the beginning is allocated for training and learning. Thus, LF is set to four months.</p>	<p>The purpose of the evaluation at this pilot phase is to assess if there is any significant impact of the SPI initiatives to the Process and Project level. Therefore, DF which is needed to assist the determination of periodic evaluation is not required at this phase.</p>	<p>After the first four months from the SPI initiatives implementation.</p>
Process	<p>4 months</p> <p>Due to the fact that the software process is tightly coupled with the projects in the development, the same LF is taken from Project and being applied here.</p>	<p>After the first four months from the SPI initiatives implementation.</p>		

Figure 4: Evaluation scheduling for Phase I

As illustrated in Figure 4, Project I and Project II are not considered for evaluation because they are within the time bound of the LF. Thus, only Project III and Project IV will be evaluated at the end of December 2006.

1.2.5 Implementation – Establishment of measurement program

The metrics from the derivation of metrics step are investigated to find out which ones are reusable and which ones are new and have not been implemented or used within One Solution (Table 11). The metrics are then established using previous knowledge and guidelines for measurement program establishment that One Solution already has.

Table 11: Phase I: New and reusable metrics

Measurement levels	Reusable/existing metrics	New metrics to be implemented
Process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M01_PRC: PCE for Phase <i>i</i> 2. M03_PRC: Defect removal efficiency before Unit Test 3. M04_PRC: Defect removal efficiency 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M02_PRC: Defect detection effectiveness before system test 2. M05_PRC: Checklist-based rating for each process
Project	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M01_PRJ: Defect density for Phase <i>i</i> 2. M02_PRJ: Total project effort normalized by project size 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M03_PRJ: Project cycle-time normalized by project size

1.2.6 Implementation – Conduct evaluation

After the metrics that are required for the purpose of evaluations have been incorporated in the existing measurement program of the Internet Banking Department, the evaluations are conducted according to the plan and schedule. One evaluation is conducted both at the Process and Project level at the end of December 2006. The results of the evaluation are grouped according to the measurement level and they are depicted in the illustrations below:

Process Level Evaluation Results – Phase I

Figure 5: Process level evaluation results for Phase I

Figure 5 shows the summary of the evaluation results in the Process level. Each of the used metrics in the evaluation is shown with its properties, success indicator, actual evaluation result, baseline value (if any) and the stakeholders (viewpoints) who are interested to see the result. Each metric is displayed in a dashboard diagram with three segments. The midpoint of the yellow segment is the baseline value against which the actual value is compared. The red and green segments represent decline and improvement respectively and are defined by the Deviation Range defined in the *Metric Form*.

A total of 10 metrics are evaluated in the Process level; three of them (M05_PRC) are not meant for success indication but are used to assess the process conformance. From the obtained evaluation results, the effectiveness and efficiency show an indication that the SPI initiatives are giving a positive impact to the process. The stakeholders (SPI Coordinator, Development Team and Head of Department) are all pleased with the results. They feel confident that the SPI initiatives will be able to improve their current processes when they are going to be implemented in Phase II to all projects in the Internet Banking System development.

Figure 6: Project level evaluation results for Phase I

Figure 6 above shows the summary of the evaluation results in the Project level. A total of seven metrics are evaluated in the Project level and five of them (M01_PRJ) belong to the same category of metrics (one for each development phase). The defect density metrics show a positive indication because the number of defects that are found during the each phase decreased. On the other hand, the effort and schedule metrics show a slight increase and this is probably due to the overhead of the introduction of the SPI initiatives. However, the extra overhead was found to be not significant with respect to the magnitude of the process change that was implemented. In general, the evaluation results show a positive impact as a result of the SPI initiatives in the Project level.

1.2.7 Implementation – Holistic view creation

In this phase's evaluation, no holistic view is created because the purpose of this phase is to pilot the SPI initiatives in the Internet Banking Department. The piloting is intended to assess the adaptability of the SPI initiatives in the projects of One Solution. Furthermore, the improvement from the SPI initiatives seen in this phase's evaluation is not significant to be presented to upper management for cost-benefit analysis or any kind of decision making.

1.2.8 Evolution – Evaluation feedback analysis

In this stage, the entire evaluation process for the first phase is evaluated. The post-mortem analysis is held in a meeting with the evaluation team who conducted the evaluation and with the representatives of the stakeholders (viewpoints). The meeting is aimed to detect problems in the evaluation process and to elaborate solutions for those issues in order to refine the evaluation process for the next phase.

During the meeting, issues about the sufficiency of the metrics used are discussed. The Project Managers feel that there is a need to identify more metrics for Phase II implementation in order to increase the confidence level on the gained improvements. The Head of Department also agrees with the Project Managers and suggests including productivity metrics to assess the impact of the SPI initiatives on the staff's performance. The SPI Coordinator, on the other hand, suggests to include statistical analysis such as control charts to evaluate the trend of the defect metrics over the time.

Aside from the above discussions, the stakeholders also discuss problems in the data collection mechanisms on the target entities. The evaluation team who was supposed to gather the data relies too much on the people from the projects which are supposed to report the data. This has led to a delay in the evaluation process because people from the projects tend to forget and delaying the task. In the next phase, the evaluation team is advised to act more actively by collecting data in the target entity, paying attention not to interrupt the ongoing development process while doing it.

1.3 Phase II

In this phase, the SPI initiatives are expanded to be implemented in all projects within Internet Banking System development. The aim of the implementation is aligned with the improvement goals of the SPI initiatives, that is, to improve the product quality and achieve a shorter time-to-deliver. In order to shorten the scenario and limit redundancy, only the Product level is discussed in detail for each step since Process and Project level were already shown in Phase I.

1.3.1 Design – Evaluation scoping

In this step, scoping for Process, Project and Product levels is conducted. Stakeholders that are interested to see the results in these levels are the Development Team of Internet Banking projects, Project Managers of Internet Banking projects, the SPI Coordinator, Internet Banking Product Managers, the Head of the Process Group, the Head of the Internet Banking Department, and the Head of R&D. Table 12 shows how these viewpoints are mapped to the measurement levels and the following paragraphs describe the rationale for this mapping.

In Process level, the SPI Coordinator coordinates the implementation of initiatives for all projects within the Internet Banking Department. Therefore, he needs to see the evaluation results in order to judge the impact in this larger scale. In this phase, the Head of Internet Banking Department is convinced about the improvement and he passes the sponsorship to the Head of the Process Group. He, as the superior of the SPI Coordinator and the person who decided which initiatives to implement, needs to know how they perform in this larger scope, that is, in the whole Internet Baking Department. The Development Teams of Internet Banking projects are also interested to see the evaluation results at this level so that they can see the effect of their actions and the results can motivate them to work along with the improvement initiatives.

In the Project level, Project Managers of Internet Banking projects, as the ones who coordinate the entire processes in the Internet Banking projects, need to see the evaluation results such that they can judge the improvement and impact on the projects in general. The Head of Internet Banking Department as the superior of Project Managers needs to see the results of the evaluation since he wants to know whether the initiatives bring benefits in his department or not. The Development Teams of Internet Banking need to see the results in this level to get motivated for and stay committed with the improvement initiatives.

In the Product level, Product Managers in Internet Banking Department need to see the evaluation results so they can gauge the impact of the initiatives in their products. The Head of R&D who supervises all products of One Solution also needs to know the improvement in Internet Banking products because Internet Banking is one of the companies' major products and has to be monitored closely. Another reason is that the Head of R&D has to take the decision whether the improvement initiatives are worth to be implemented in Phase III, in which the initiatives will be implemented in the remaining departments. The Project Team of Internet Banking needs to see the evaluation results because they participate in the projects that build up the products. Therefore, they must be aware of the effects of the initiatives in the products such that they stay committed to the initiatives in their daily work.

Table 12: Phase II: *Evaluation Area Table*

Measurement Levels	Viewpoints		
	<i>Implementer</i>	<i>Coordinator</i>	<i>Sponsor</i>
Process	Development Team (Architect, Analyst, Programmer, Tester)	SPI Coordinator	Head of Process Group
Project	Development Team (Architect, Analyst, Programmer, Tester)	Project Managers (Internet Banking System)	Head of Department (Internet Banking System)

Product	Project Team (Project Manager and Development Team)	Product Managers (Internet Banking System)	Head of R&D
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1.3.2 Design – Determination of measures

Similar to Phase I, the determination of measures is separated according to the two improvement goals. Since the determinations of metrics for the Process and Project measurement levels has been shown in Phase I, only the necessary steps for the Product level are shown. For BG1: Improve product quality the GQM Construction Table (Table 13) is created and the GQM approach applied as shown in Table 14. The same approach is followed for BG2: Decrease time-to-deliver as shown in Table 15 and Table 16 respectively.

Table 13: Phase II: *GQM Construction Table* for BG1

Purpose:	Evaluate			
Business Goal (Improvement Goal):	BG1: Improve product quality			
Object of Study:	CMMI: 1. Peer Review Process 2. Unit Test Planning 3. Development Integration Testing 4. Support Tool for Software Development			
Context:	Projects in Internet Banking System development			
Measurement Level	Point of View (Viewpoint)	Category	Focus (Success Indicator)	Measurement Goal
Product	Product Manager	Primary	Quality	MG01_PRD
		Complementary	Time-to-market	MG02_PRD
			Cost	MG03_PRD
	Project Team	Primary	Quality	MG04_PRD
	Head of R&D	Primary	Quality	MG05_PRD
		Complementary	Time-to-market	MG06_PRD
			Cost	MG07_PRD

Table 14: Phase II: *Measurement Goal, Question(s) and Metrics* for BG1

<p>MG01_PRD: Quality Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their impact on the quality on the products developed within the Internet Banking from the Product Manager point of view.</p> <p>Question 1: What is the product quality of the final software delivered to customers?</p> <p>Metrics:</p>

M01_PRD:**Post-release fault density**

Post-release fault density = F / S

F = Number of failures encountered by customer during operation

S = Size of the delivered product in KLOC

This metric shows the product quality in terms of the failures during operation. The introduced SPI initiatives are expected to help in capturing more defects in the products before releasing them to customers and therefore reduced the customer reported failures.

Question 2: How reliable is the final delivered product during operation?

Metrics:**M02_PRD:****Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)**

MTBF = Sum of all differences between uptime and downtime / Number of failures

This metric shows the reliability of the product during operation. The longer the time period between failures, the higher is the reliability of the system. The metric is using the total uptime of the system as the numerator and divides it by the number of failures to get an average value.

Question 3: What is the customer satisfaction on the features delivered in the final product?

Metrics:**M03_PRD:**

Percentage of delivered features = $\text{Implemented} / \text{Total}$

Percentage of delivered features = I / R

I = Number of features implemented

R = Total number of features in the requirements

This metric can be used to indicate the customer satisfaction in terms of the fulfilment of the requirements that are agreed in the contract.

M04_PRD:**Customer satisfaction survey**

In order to effectively evaluate the customer satisfaction, one of the best ways is to hear it from the voice of the customers themselves. This can be done by preparing a customer satisfaction survey addressing the achieved product quality.

MG02_PRD: Time-to-market

Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their impact on the time-to-delivery of the products within the Internet Banking development from the Product Manager point of view.

Question 1: What is the time that is needed to deliver a product to customer?

Metrics:**M05_PRD:****Time-to-deliver**

Time-to-deliver = Time elapsed between the system requirements conception and deployment.

The typical product development in One Solution consists of 1-3 projects. Therefore, the product development time is highly dependent on the schedule of the projects involved in the product development.

MG03_PRD: Cost

Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their impact on the cost of the products within the Internet Banking development from the Product Manager point of view.

Question 1: What is the cost involved of developing the product?

Metrics:**M06_PRD:****Relative cost of System Test**

Relative cost of System Test = $T / P * 100\%$

T = Product testing effort involved, that refers specifically to System Testing after the features from all the projects are integrated.

P = Overall product development effort

Effort is calculated in man-hours

The SPI initiatives are aimed to contain more defects in earlier phases of the development and therefore it is expected that System Testing requires less effort and resources.

M07_PRD:**Cost of rework**

Cost of rework normalized by size = E / S

E = Total effort of fixing the defects; in man-hours

S = Product size in KLOC

The SPI initiatives are expected to reduce the numbers of defects and thus the cost of rework, i.e. the cost of fixing defects, is expected to be reduced too.

MG04_PRD: Quality

Reuse of Question 1 and its Metric from MG01_PRD, point of view is the Project Team.

MG05_PRD: Quality

Reuse of Question 3 and its Metric from MG01_PRD, point of view is the Head of R&D.

MG06_PRD: Time-to-market

Reuse of the same Question and Metric from MG02_PRD, point of view is the Head of R&D.

MG07_PRD: Cost

Evaluate the SPI initiatives in terms of their impact on the cost of the products within the Internet Banking development from the Head of R&D point of view.

Question 1: What is the total cost of the product?

Metrics:**M08_PRD:****Product cost normalized by size**

Product cost normalized by size = $(E + M) / S$

E = Total effort for the whole product life cycle in man-month

M = Maintenance cost that involves the cost of fixing post-release defects and all the necessary support cost calculated in man-month

S = Product size in KLOC

Although cost is not the improvement goal of the SPI initiatives, it is still a major concern to the Head of R&D. He would be interested to see if the SPI initiatives would give any positive impact to the cost of the product in the long-run.

Table 15: Phase II: *GQM Construction Table* for BG2

Purpose:	Evaluate			
Business Goal (Improvement Goal):	BG2: Decrease time-to-deliver			
Object of Study:	CMMI: 1. Peer Review Process 2. Unit Test Planning 3. Development Integration Testing 4. Support Tool for Software Development			
Context:	Projects in Internet Banking System development			
Measurement Level	Point of View (Viewpoint)	Category	Focus (Success Indicator)	Measurement Goal
Product	Product Manager	Primary	Time-to-market	MG08_PRD
		Complementary	Quality	MG09_PRD
			Cost	MG10_PRD
	Project Team	Primary	Time-to-market	MG11_PRD
	Head of R&D	Primary	Time-to-market	MG12_PRD
		Complementary	Quality	MG13_PRD
			Cost	MG14_PRD

Table 16: Phase II: *Measurement Goal, Question(s) and Metrics* for BG2

<p>MG08_PRD: Time-to-market Reusing the same Question and Metric from MG02_PRD, point of view is the Product Manager.</p>
<p>MG09_PRD: Quality Reusing the same Questions and Metrics from MG01_PRD, point of view is the Product Manager.</p>
<p>MG10_PRD: Cost Reusing the same Questions and Metrics from MG03_PRD, point of view is the Product Manager.</p>
<p>MG11_PRD: Time-to-market Reusing the same Question and Metric from MG02_PRD, point of view is the Project Team.</p>
<p>MG12_PRD: Time-to-market Reusing the same Question and Metric from MG02_PRD, point of view is the Head of R&D.</p>
<p>MG13_PRD: Quality Reusing Question 3 and its metrics from MG01_PRD, point of view is the Head of R&D.</p>
<p>MG14_PRD: Cost Reusing the same Question and Metric from MG07_PRD, point of view is the Head of R&D.</p>

In Figure 7 the GQM Tree for the Product measurement level is given. It illustrates how the elicited metrics can be traced back to the respective measurement and business goals.

GQM Tree for Phase II (Product only)

Figure 7: GQM tree for Phase II (Product only)

1.3.3 Design – Selection of evaluation methods

In Phase I, some examples of metrics in *Metric Form* for Process and Project level have been shown. Here, only two metrics for the Product level are shown (Table 17 and Table 18) for the sake of brevity.

Table 17: Phase II: *Metric Form* for M04_PRD

Metric Form	
Metric ID	: M04_PRD
Metric Name	: Customer satisfaction survey
Success Indicator	: Quality
Measurement Goal (Viewpoint)	: i. MG01_PRD (Product Manager) ii. MG05_PRD (Head of R&D) iii. MG09_PRD (Product Manager) iv. MG09_PRD (Head of R&D)
Measurement Level	: Product
Algorithm / Description	: In order to effectively evaluate the customer satisfaction, one of the best ways is to hear it from the voice of the customers themselves. This can be done by preparing a customer satisfaction survey addressing the achieved product quality. Example: The customer satisfaction survey can be designed using Likert

	<p>Scales consisting of questions about the functionality, usability, and other quality attributes while using the product.</p>
Baseline Value	<p>: The baseline for the customer satisfaction survey can be obtained from similar surveys that were previously conducted from past product releases. Based on the data from past surveys, the customer satisfaction was rated as Average.</p>
Deviation Range	<p>: N/A</p>
Evaluation Method	<p>: Survey (Questionnaire)</p> <p>Objective: The objective of the evaluation is aimed to find out if the quality of the product got affected in a positive way as a result of the implementation of the SPI initiatives.</p>
Confounding Factor(s)	<p>: While conducting survey, the following factors should be taken into consideration in the evaluation:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evaluation sampling (New or existing target customers for survey) 2. Subjects' domain (Different industry or domains have different levels of expectation towards the product) 3. Subjective evaluation (Different customer have different levels of expectations) 4. Degree of usage (Number of features actually used, total usage time, maturity of usage)

Table 18: Phase II: *Metric Form* for M08_PRD

Metric Form	
Metric ID	: M08_PRD
Metric Name	: Product cost normalized by size
Success Indicator	: Cost
Measurement Goal (Viewpoint)	: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. MG07_PRD (Head of R&D) ii. MG14_PRD (Head of R&D)
Measurement Level	: Product
Algorithm / Description	<p>Product cost = $(E + M) / S$</p> <p>E = Total effort for the whole product life cycle in man-month M = Maintenance cost that involves the cost of fixing post-release defects and all the necessary support cost calculated in man-month S = Product size in KLOC</p> <p>Although cost is not the improvement goal of the SPI initiatives, it is still a major concern to the Head of R&D. He would be interested to see if the SPI initiatives would give any positive impact to the cost of the product in the long-run.</p> <p>Example: The total effort needed for the development of the product is 10 man-months and the maintenance/support cost after the delivery of the product to customer is 4 man-months. If the product size is 20 KLOC, then the product cost normalized by size is calculated as $(10 + 4) / 20 = 0.7$ man-months per KLOC.</p>

Baseline Value	:	The baselines for this metric can be computed based on the data collected from previous projects or calculated from current projects (without the SPI initiative implemented) that are running. Based on the historical data in the organization, the baseline value for product cost is 1.2 man-months per KLOC.
Deviation Range	:	The deviation range is set to $\pm 10\%$
Evaluation Method	:	Pre-post comparison Objective: The objective of the evaluation is aimed to find out if the SPI initiatives are able to reduce the product cost in general as a result from the savings of defects containment effectiveness during development.
Confounding Factor(s)	:	During pre-post comparison, the following factors should be taken into consideration in the evaluation: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project size and complexity (No. of features) 2. Technology factors (Language, tool, environment, platform) 3. Employee factors (Level of experience, turnover) 4. Process Compliance (Degree of process conformance implemented and followed)

1.3.4 Design – Evaluation scheduling

After the required metrics have been defined, the evaluation on the products within the Internet Banking System development can now be scheduled as shown in Table 19.

Table 19: Phase II: *Evaluation Scheduling Form* for Product

Duration:	Starting from January 2007 onwards			
Context:	The SPI initiatives are implemented in the whole Internet Banking System Department and are applied across all the products that are developed in that department. At the time to evaluate, the candidate products to be evaluated will be chosen based on the products schedule that are active at that point in time.			
Time to evaluate / Periodic evaluation	Measurement Levels	Lag Factor (LF)	Degradation Factor (DF)	Time to Evaluate
	Product	5 months The usual product cycle time is four months. However, it needs to be considered when the customer feedback might be available to integrate it in the evaluation. Therefore, the LF is set to be one month later after the product is released to customer.	4 months Since the usual product release cycle is four months, the product release cycle time is taken as the DF to enforce a periodic evaluation after every product release.	4 months The first evaluation shall be done after the first five months and periodic evaluations shall be done no later than four months after the first evaluation. In this case, the evaluation will be conducted every four months.

Figure 8: Product's evaluation scheduling for Phase II

Figure 8 illustrates the product's evaluation scheduling for Phase II. The candidate target entity (product) to be evaluated at the scheduled date will be chosen based on the product's schedule that are active at that point in time.

1.3.5 Implementation – Establishment of measurement program

As in Phase I, the elicited metrics are investigated to find out which ones are reusable and which ones are new and have not been implemented or yet used within One Solution (Table 20). The metrics are then established using previous knowledge and guidelines for measurement program establishment that One Solution already has.

Table 20: Phase II: New and reusable metrics

Measurement levels	Reusable/existing metrics	New metrics to be implemented
Product	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> M01_PRD: Post-release fault density M04_PRD: Customer Satisfaction Survey M05_PRD: Time-to-Deliver M08_PRD: Product cost normalized by size 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> M02_PRD: Mean Time Between Failures M03_PRD: Percentage of delivered features M06_PRD: Relative cost of System Test M07_PRD: Cost of rework normalized by size

1.3.6 Implementation – Conduct evaluation

For the sake of brevity, only the Product evaluation results are shown. The evaluations are conducted as according to the schedule on the Products that were active at the time of evaluation.

Figure 9 shows the summary of the evaluation results in the Product level. From the evaluation results obtained on the four metrics, the overall product quality shows a positive indication of improvement. The customer satisfaction survey turned out to give a very positive indication whereas the percentage of delivered features slightly dropped. Regarding the other two success indicators (time-to-market and cost), both show a good sign of improvement after one year. All the stakeholders, especially the Head of R&D, are satisfied

with the results and the organization is ready to further expand the implementation of SPI initiatives to the other two major products of One Solution.

In order to see a better representation of evaluation results, the next step in the scenario presents the holistic view creation that shows the subjective value of the improvement from different viewpoints.

Figure 9: Product level evaluation results for Phase II

1.3.7 Implementation – Holistic view creation

At the end of year 2007, One Solution created a holistic view for each measurement level, showing the different subjective values of the improvement from different viewpoints. Every stakeholder that is interested to see and evaluate the improvement initiatives was involved in the activity of rating the metrics in order to come out with the final holistic views.

Since the impact rating of the improvement is subjective in nature, there was a meeting between the stakeholders to define guidelines on how to perform the rating with the aim to

improve the consistency in the rating outcomes. The impact rating is based on a Likert Scale from -5.0 up to +5.0 as shown in Table 21.

Table 21: Impact rating guidelines

Impact Rating (IR)	Value	Description
High gain	+5.0	Significant improvements observed. Actual values of improvements usually above 40% with respect to baseline.
Considerably high gain	+4.0	Improvements recorded in between high gain and moderate gain range.
Moderate gain	+3.0	The initiatives show an average gain. Actual values of improvements usually around 20% above baseline.
Considerably low gain	+2.0	Improvements recorded in between moderate gain and low gain range.
Low gain	+1.0	There is slight improvement visible. Actual values of improvements usually around 10% above baseline.
No impact	0.0	There is no significant impact observed. Usually the actual values that varies less than 5% above or below the baseline fall in this category.
Low loss	-1.0	There is slight loss visible from the improvement initiatives. Actual values usually around 10% below baseline.
Considerably low loss	-2.0	Decline in actual values recorded in between moderate loss and low loss range.
Moderate loss	-3.0	The initiatives show an average negative impact. Actual values of improvements usually worsen around 20% below baseline.
Considerably high loss	-4.0	Decline in actual values recorded in between high loss and moderate loss range.
High loss	-5.0	Significant decline observed. Actual values usually worsen by around 40% with respect to baseline.

Note: Table 21 only applies to One Solution and it cannot be used in other companies. The descriptions in the impact rating are mostly discussing on the percentage of changes. However, there are some metrics that are not objective in nature in which they cannot really be judged in an objective manner. The table only serves as a guideline and the impact rating is still subject to the interpretation of the individual viewpoints.

Table 22 shows the details of the subjective value of improvement calculation that takes into account the subjective weight of the metrics together with its impact rating. Similar calculations were performed for the Process and Project level and based on the obtained values; the holistic views for Process, Project and Product level are illustrated in the Figure 10.

Table 22: Holistic view calculation for Product

Viewpoint	Metrics	Subjective Weight (SW)	Impact Rating (IR)	Subjective Value of Improvement (SVI)
Head of R&D (Sponsor)	M03_PRD	0.10	0.0	$[(0.10)(0.0) + (0.40)(+4.0) + (0.40)(+2.0) + (0.10)(+1.0)] = +2.50$
	M04_PRD	0.40	+4.0	
	M05_PRD	0.40	+2.0	
	M08_PRD	0.10	+1.0	
Product Managers (Coordinator)	M01_PRD	0.10	+3.0	$[(0.10)(+3.0) + (0.10)(0.0) + (0.15)(-1.0) + (0.25)(+3.0) + (0.25)(+2.0) + (0.05)(+2.0) + (0.10)(+1.0)] = +1.60$
	M02_PRD	0.10	0.0	
	M03_PRD	0.15	-1.0	
	M04_PRD	0.25	+3.0	
	M05_PRD	0.25	+2.0	
	M06_PRD	0.05	+2.0	
	M07_PRD	0.10	+1.0	
Project Team (Implementer)	M01_PRD	0.60	+3.0	$[(0.60)(+3.0) + (0.40)(+1.0)] = +2.20$
	M05_PRD	0.40	+1.0	

Holistic View for Process

Holistic View for Project

Holistic View for Product

Figure 10: Holistic view presentation for the Process, Project and Product level

From the holistic views in Figure 10, the SPI initiatives implementation can be rated as successful because all three Process, Project and Product level show a positive impact from the point of view of all the stakeholders. It is interesting to see that in different measurement levels, the stakeholders who are most satisfied in the respective levels differs from one another; Implementer is most satisfied in the Process, Coordinator is most satisfied in the Project while the Sponsor is most satisfied in the Project and Product level. The company is now in a good situation to roll out the initiatives to a wider scope since all stakeholders perceive benefits from the change.

1.3.8 Evolution – Evaluation feedback analysis

In this stage, the post-mortem analysis for the second phase evaluation is conducted. The stakeholders and the evaluation team had a meeting to discuss the existing issues along with the solutions.

The first discussed issue is concerning the Customer Satisfaction Survey. The evaluation team lacks of members who possess the required experience to conduct the survey efficiently. The proposed solution for this problem is to recruit personnel who are qualified in conducting surveys or to train the evaluation team for conducting future surveys.

The second discussed issue discussed in the meeting concerns the confidence on the evaluation results. The stakeholders feel that the confidence in the evaluation results should be improved. They suggest implementing cross-examination in the next phase for the three measurement levels.

1.4 Phase III

In this phase, the initiatives are expanded to two new products, Loan System and Deposit System products. The aim of this phase is to implement the initiatives organization-wide, as the requirement of CMMI is to implement standardized processes at the organizational level. The description about this phase's evaluation will be presented by giving a summary of the stages and only the main outcomes of each stage are illustrated.

1.4.1 Design stage

This stage consists of four steps but only the outcome of two steps will be presented, evaluation scoping and determination of measures. The evaluation method and evaluation scheduling in this phase are not discussed here because the same activities were already explained in the previous two phases. For evaluation scoping and the determination of measures, only Organization and External levels are shown.

In evaluation scoping, three stakeholders are identified: the Board of Directors, Development Departments (Head of R&D, Head of Department, and Project Team) and the Company Shareholders. In determining the measures, these stakeholders come out with the success indicators that are considered as important from their point of view and the steps involved in deriving those measures are similar to the previous phases. Table 23 shows the combined outcome for the Organization and External level.

Table 23: Success indicators and metrics for Organization and External level

Improvement Goal:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve product quality 2. Decrease time-to-deliver 			
SPI Initiatives:	CMMI: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Peer Review Process 2. Unit Test Planning 3. Development Integration Testing 4. Support Tool for Software Development 			
Context:	Development in the following products: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internet Banking System 2. Loan System 3. Deposit System 			
Measurement Level	Point of View (Viewpoint)	Success Indicator	Metrics	
Organization	Coordinator: Board of Directors	Economic	M01_ORG: Return-on-investment (ROI)	
		Growth	M02_ORG: Product sales revenue growth	
		Employee	M03_ORG: Employee satisfaction survey	
	Implementer: Development Departments (Head of R&D, Head of Department, Project Team)	Growth	M02_ORG: Product sales revenue growth	
		Sponsor: Company Shareholders	Economic	M01_ORG: Return-on-investment (ROI)
			Growth	M02_ORG: Product sales revenue growth
Employee	M03_ORG: Employee satisfaction survey			
External	Coordinator: Board of Directors	Customer	M01_EXT: Operation productivity	
	Sponsor: Company Shareholders	Customer	M02_EXT: Operation efficiency	

1.4.2 Implementation stage

In this stage, only the holistic view creation step is presented as the other steps are similar with the ones from previous phases with the only difference on the used target entities and measures. At the end of year 2008, One Solution conducted another holistic view evaluation of the improvement in all measurement levels. In order to have a “one-view” representation of the improvement, the individual holistic views at each measurement level are combined into an average value of improvement, AVI, for each measurement level. Figure 11 shows the combined holistic view for all measurement levels. Overall, the SPI initiatives have shown a very positive impact to One Solution with all the measurement levels showing some degree of improvement after two years of implementation. The inner measurement levels, the Process and Project levels show the most visible impact from the improvement initiatives as compared to the other levels.

Combined Holistic View of Improvement

Figure 11: Combined holistic view presentation

1.4.3 Evolution stage

In this stage, a post-mortem analysis is conducted to evaluate the evaluation process of Phase III.

The first issue discussed during the meeting is concerning the evaluation scheduling for the Organization and External level. The stakeholders feel that the evaluation for these two levels was conducted too early, and therefore, it failed to show significant improvements in the Organization level as they were expected. The evaluation team also realizes this problem and agrees to change the evaluation schedule for these two measurement levels.

The second discussed issue concerns the entities where the evaluation team collected the data for the External level. The evaluation team sampled two clients of One Solution to get the data. The stakeholders propose to get the data from all of their clients. However, this idea is quite difficult to be carried out as One Solution’s clients are more than 20 companies and dispersed in many countries. Therefore, it will cost too much to gather data from all clients for the evaluation process. Finally, it is agreed to sample four clients from different countries.